

ARTICLE

Identification of Active Sites on Platinum Alloys for the Electroreduction of Oxygen

Received 00th January 20xx,
Accepted 00th January 20xx

DOI: 10.1039/x0xx00000x

Regina M. Kluge,^a Richard W. Haid,^a Alexander Riss,^b Yang Bao,^b Knud Seufert,^b Thorsten O. Schmidt,^a Batyr Garlyyev,^a Johannes V. Barth,^b Francesco Allegretti,^{b,*} Willi Auwärter,^{b,*} Federico Calle-Vallejo,^{c,*} Aliaksandr S. Bandarenka^{a,d,*}

This document is the submitted manuscript version before revision of a published work that appeared in the final form in Regina M. Kluge, Richard W. Haid, Alexander Riss, Yang Bao, Knud Seufert, Thorsten O. Schmidt, Sebastian A. Watzel, Johannes V. Barth, Francesco Allegretti, Willi Auwärter, Federico Calle-Vallejo, Aliaksandr S. Bandarenka, **A trade-off between ligand and strain effects optimizes the oxygen reduction activity of Pt alloys. *Energy Environ. Sci.*, 2022, 15, 5181-5191. doi.org/10.1039/D2EE01850K**

In the course of optimizing the performance of catalytic materials, elucidating the dependence of the chemical reactivity on the atomic arrangement of the catalyst surface is paramount. Therefore, identifying the active sites, which provide optimal binding of intermediates, is the first step toward rational catalyst design. In this work, we turn our interest to the oxygen reduction reaction (ORR), which is an important constituent of many energy provision and storage devices. Among the state-of-the-art ORR catalysts is platinum (Pt) and its alloys; the latter benefit from so-called ligand and strain effects. In particular, we report the identification of active sites on Pt₃Ni(111) in an acidic medium *via an in-situ* technique based on electrochemical scanning tunnelling microscopy. We identify Pt₃Ni(111) terraces as the most active sites, while step sites show activity to a comparable or lesser extent. Furthermore, we devise the mathematical model of alloy- and strain-sensitive generalized coordination numbers, which assess both the composition and geometric configuration of optimal catalytic active sites. The ligand effects and lattice compression resulting from the alloying of Pt with 3d transition metals increases the generalized coordination number of surface Pt atoms, which deactivates concave sites and makes (111) terrace sites highly active. With this efficient combination of theoretical and experimental tools, we are able to provide guidelines for rational catalyst design on Pt alloys for the oxygen electroreduction.

Introduction

On the route to a “green” way of energy provision and storage, electrochemical devices such as hydrogen fuel cells and metal-air batteries are among the key technologies.^{1,2,3} However, their optimization requires an in-depth understanding of the electrochemical processes at the electrified solid/liquid

interfaces. *In-situ* and *in-operando* techniques together with mathematical modelling are most suitable to assess the nature of the active sites.

A stumbling block for the mentioned examples of electrochemical devices are the sluggish kinetics of the oxygen reduction reaction (ORR). Currently, the state-of-the-art ORR catalysts are mostly based on platinum (Pt). For the past two decades, trends in the catalytic activity of surface sites have often been extracted from activity measurements on well-defined crystal planes and computational models according to the Sabatier principle.^{4,5,6,7} For pure Pt, measurements on stepped single crystals^{8,9} indicated highly coordinated sites in the vicinity of undercoordinated sites as the most active for the ORR.^{10,11,12} These results are in line with the high activity of concave Pt nanoparticles.^{13,14,15,16,17} However, from experimental measurements and a theoretical point of view, Pt(111) does not offer optimal binding conditions for adsorbed hydroxyl and hydroperoxyl intermediates (*OH and *OOH).¹ In

^a Physik-Department ECS, Technische Universität München, James-Franck-Straße 1, 85748 Garching, Germany.

^b Physik-Department E20, Technische Universität München, James-Franck-Straße 1, 85748 Garching, Germany.

^c Department of Materials Science and Chemical Physics & Institute of Theoretical and Computational Chemistry (IQTCUB), University of Barcelona, Martí i Franquès 1, 08028 Barcelona, Spain.

^d Catalysis Research Center TUM, Ernst-Otto-Fischer-Straße 1, 85748 Garching, Germany

* Corresponding authors' e-mails:

(F. A.) francesco.allegretti@tum.de

(W.A.) wau@tum.de

(F. C.-V.) f.calle.vallejo@ub.edu

(A.S.B.) bandarenka@ph.tum.de

Electronic Supplementary Information (ESI) available: Additional n-EC-STM measurements; details on the calculation approach. See DOI: 10.1039/x0xx00000x

fact, an optimal ORR catalyst requires an *OH binding of ~0.1-0.15 eV weaker than Pt(111).^{1,10,18,19,20}

A common approach to lower the binding energy of the ORR intermediates is the alloying of Pt with early (*e.g.* Sc, Y) or late (*e.g.* Fe, Co, Ni, Cu) transition metals (M).^{18,21,22,23,24,25} Inspired by the discovery of the exceptional ORR activity of Pt₃Ni(111) in acidic medium,¹³ several groups have synthesized Pt_xNi nanoparticles with high performance.^{26,27,28,29} The type and amount of alloying material has a considerable impact on the ORR activity (a detailed summary is given in reference [30]). The superior performance of Pt alloy catalysts compared to pure Pt is often explained by the presence of so-called ligand and strain effects. Ligand effects arise from the combination of Pt with dissimilar neighbouring atoms, which influence their electronic structure and adsorption behaviour.^{31,32} Strain effects originate from different interatomic distances at the surface compared to the bulk of pure Pt.^{33,34,35}

Although it is widely accepted that ligand and strain effects play a key role in the superior ORR performance of Pt-alloys, the nature of the active sites remains elusive. In order to contribute in filling this void, we investigate Pt₃Ni(111) under reaction conditions in an acidic medium with electrochemical scanning tunnelling microscopy (EC-STM). The method is able to identify active sites with a resolution on the nanometre scale by noise features in the EC-STM signal.^{11,12,36,37,38,39,40,41} By introducing a reaction at the electrode/electrolyte interface, the tunnelling barrier experiences spatial and time-dependent changes. Since the recorded STM signal and its stability is mainly governed by the tunnelling barrier and its properties, the noise arising under these conditions can be interpreted as a perturbation induced by a catalytic current.⁴² In short, an increase in the noise level in the STM signal indicates the position of active sites, and can even reveal quantitative information about the local activity.^{12,42} Applying “noise”-EC-STM (n-EC-STM) to Pt₃Ni(111) electrodes under reaction conditions, we find (111) terrace sites as the most active for the ORR. Furthermore, we observe sites of different coordination such as step sites with either slightly inferior or comparable activity to the (111) terrace sites. To support the experimental data, we devise a numerical model based on alloy-sensitive generalized coordination numbers to quantify strain and ligand effects in geometric terms. According to this model, both overcoordinated and undercoordinated defects lower the activity on Pt₃Ni(111), which is in line with the experimental observations. Notably, the approach of generalized coordination numbers developed here can be applied to a wider range of Pt₃M alloys (in this work to Pt₃Co and PtCu near-surface alloys). Since the findings on the alloy materials deviate substantially from the case of pure Pt(111), we emphasise the importance of our study, in which the combination of an experimental *in-situ* method and the model of alloy-sensitive generalized coordination numbers gives directions for optimal ORR electrocatalysts.

Methods

Experimental Details

Sample Preparation. Prior to the electrochemical measurements, the Pt₃Ni(111) single crystal (Ø 5 mm, MaTeck) was sputter-cleaned under ultra-high vacuum (UHV) conditions using an Ar⁺-beam of 10 µA ion current and 1 kV energy. It was annealed for 10 min after each sputtering step and the temperature was stepwise increased up to 1050 K. After the last annealing step, the sample was slowly cooled down to room temperature.

LEED. A commercial low-energy electron diffraction (LEED) apparatus (SPECTALEED, Omicron NanoTechnology GmbH) was employed to assess the quality of the surface order in a dedicated UHV chamber operating at a base pressure of *approx.* 3 × 10⁻¹⁰ mbar. The chamber contained ancillary facilities for surface cleaning and sample preparation.

LT-STM. Low temperature scanning tunnelling microscopy (LT-STM) experiments were performed using a CreaTec instrument under UHV conditions (*p* ≈ 10⁻¹⁰ mbar) at a temperature of 6 K. The sample was prepared by cycles of argon ion sputtering (at 1 kV) and annealing at a maximal temperature of 1050 K. For selected preparations, CO was dosed onto the surface to help with tip preparation. Images were recorded in constant-current mode; the respective imaging parameters are given in the figure captions. The images were subjected to standard corrections, *i.e.*, plane-subtraction, global brightness/contrast adjustments, and to fast Fourier transformation (FFT) filtering. The images were processed using the Nanonis image viewer software and the WSxM software⁴³.

Electrochemical Measurements. The quality of the crystal was probed by performing cyclic voltammetry (CV) experiments in Ar-saturated (Argon 5.0, Westfalen) electrolytes at 50 mV s⁻¹ scan rate. To study the electrocatalytic activity,⁴⁴ rotating disk electrode (RDE) (Pine Instrument Company) experiments were executed in O₂-saturated (Oxygen 4.5, Linde) solutions at 1600 rpm rotational speed and 50 mV s⁻¹ scan rate. Results were 85% *iR*-corrected for the electrolyte resistance obtained from electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements. The experiments were performed with a BioLogic VSP-300 potentiostat (BioLogic, France). The electrolyte was 0.1 M perchloric acid (HClO₄, Suprapur, Merck Germany). The potentials were recorded either against a mercury-mercurous sulphate electrode (MMS, SI Analytics, Germany) or a reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE, HydroFlex®, gaskatel, Germany). The potential values (U) were calibrated against each other via $U_{RHE} = U_{MMS} + 0.66 \text{ V} + 0.059 \text{ pH}$. The reference electrode is indicated in the indices. The electrochemical setup was completed by a Pt wire counter electrode (99.9%, Goodfellow, Germany). The cell was regularly cleaned with “Caro’s acid”, *i.e.*, a 3:1 ratio of H₂SO₄ (96%, Roth) and H₂O₂ (30%, Roth) and subsequently rinsed with boiling ultrapure water multiple times.

n-EC-STM. All n-EC-STM experiments were conducted using a commercial MultiMode EC-STM/EC-AFM scanning probe

microscope (Veeco Instruments) connected to a NanoScope III scan feedback controller and a Universal Bipotentiostat (Veeco Instruments). STM tips were mechanically ripped from a Pt80Ir20 wire (GoodFellow, \varnothing 0.25 mm) and subsequently isolated using Apiezon wax.⁴⁵ The crystal was clamped between a homemade stainless steel sample holder and a Teflon™ ring. The latter exposed a sample area of 0.126 cm² to the electrolyte. To complete the miniature four-electrode setup, reference and counter electrodes (both Pt wires, MaTeck, \varnothing 0.5 mm, 99.99 % purity) were immersed in the electrolyte next to the STM tip. Due to the small dimensions of the electrochemical cell in the STM setup, the use of a Pt wire as *quasi*-reference electrode was required. Even though a direct transfer into *e.g.* RHE-scale is not possible, its use has been proven reliable for n-EC-STM measurements.^{11,12,36,37,38,39} All measurements were conducted at room temperature with the electrolyte exposed to air. More details on the methodology of the n-EC-STM method can be found in reference [11], in the **results and discussion section** of the main text of this article and in **section S3** of the Supplementary Information (SI).

DFT Calculations

The spin-unrestricted DFT calculations were made with the Vienna *ab initio* simulation package (VASP)⁴⁶ using the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) exchange-correlation functional⁴⁷ and the projector augmented-wave (PAW) method⁴⁸. The (111) surfaces of the Pt₃Ni, Pt₃Co and PtCu near-surface alloys (NSAs) were modelled with 2×2 supercells, whereas the (533) and (221) surfaces were modelled with 2×1 supercells. All slab models contained four metal layers and were modelled based on lattice constants of 3.98 Å, 3.88 Å and 3.89 Å for PtCu NSAs, Pt₃Ni and Pt₃Co, respectively. The two topmost surface layers and the adsorbates were allowed to relax in all directions, whereas the bottommost layers were fixed at the bulk equilibrium positions. We used a plane-wave cut-off of 450 eV, $k_B T = 0.2$ eV and extrapolating the total energies to 0 K, and the conjugate-gradient optimization scheme until the maximal force on any atom was less than 0.05 eV Å⁻¹. Monkhorst-Pack meshes⁴⁹ of 6×6×1, 6×3×1 and 6×4×1 for the (111), (533) and (221) facets ensured the convergence of the adsorption energies within 0.05 eV. The vacuum layer between periodically repeated images in the vertical direction was larger than 14 Å and dipole corrections were applied. The data for Pt facets were taken from previous studies.⁵⁰ H₂O and H₂ were calculated by sampling the Γ -point only in cells of 15 Å × 10 Å × 11 Å and using $k_B T = 0.001$ eV. The computational hydrogen electrode (CHE) was used to describe the energetics of proton-electron pairs.⁵¹ We modelled the ORR via an associative pathway, in which O₂ is sequentially transformed into *OOH, *O + H₂O, *OH, and H₂O,⁵¹ see **section S5.1** in the SI. The free energies were approximated as: $\Delta G \approx \Delta E_{DFT} + \Delta ZPE - T\Delta S + \Delta E_{solvation}$, where ΔE_{DFT} is the DFT-calculated energy of reaction, ΔZPE is the zero-point energy change (calculated also with DFT making use of the harmonic oscillator approximation) and $T\Delta S$ is the entropy change at 298.15 K. As customary for ORR models based on the CHE, ΔS includes no entropy for the adsorbates and all the contributions for H₂ and H₂O.³⁴ Solvent-adsorbate interactions

were incorporated as an external correction depending on the adsorbate and the alloy. Specific values of the gas-phase, liquid-phase, and solvent-adsorbate stabilization corrections, together with the adsorption free energies and the optimized converged Cartesian coordinates can be found in the SI, **section S5.5**.

Results and discussion

Characterization of Pt₃Ni(111) and Identification of Active Sites with n-EC-STM

First, the Pt₃Ni(111) single crystal was characterized with surface science techniques and electrochemistry. Figure 1a shows a typical LEED pattern imaged on the fluorescent screen. From the arrangement of the diffraction spots, the (111) orientation of the surface is confirmed, with no evidence of reconstructions altering the surface periodicity.^{19,52} In addition, Figure 1b recounts a typical LT-STM measurement on the surface of the freshly prepared crystal, where the (111) surface can be distinguished with atomic resolution. Additional images are included in Figure S1 of the SI. As a rough estimate, the Pt-Pt interatomic distance was extracted from these images as (2.61 ± 0.07) Å. More details on how this value and its uncertainty were extracted are given in **section S1** of the SI. Assuming a literature value of 2.77 Å for Pt(111),⁵⁰ the deviation of the Pt₃Ni(111) surface from a Pt(111) surface is (5.8 ± 0.16) %. Therefore, one can suggest that strain effects play a key role in the ORR electrocatalysis.

Secondly, the electrochemical performance of the Pt₃Ni(111) was tested in 0.1 M HClO₄. The CV in Figure 1c is in good agreement with the literature, where one can see the typical surface oxidation and reduction peaks.^{13,53} The ORR performance (Figure 1d) was evaluated in an RDE experiment and a specific ORR activity of 7.6 mA cm⁻² was obtained at 0.9 V_{RHE}. This is slightly higher than in previous works⁵³ reported at room temperature. In the past, it has been observed that a pure Pt layer forms on the surface of a PtM bulk by electrochemical cycling in acidic medium. The compressive strain introduced thereby on the Pt surface leads to a downshift of the d-band centre¹³ and weaker binding of the ORR intermediates^{54,55,56} and, thus, to better ORR performance. Moreover, the dissolution of the transition metal atom (de-alloying) can induce significant changes in activity due to surface roughening and concomitant strain.⁵⁷ This behaviour would explain the good ORR activity observed here. A copper underpotential deposition and subsequent stripping experiment, which is provided in Figure S2 of the SI, indicates in addition that the surface contains only Pt after the electrochemical experiments. One can therefore assume that strain effects play an important role in the electroreduction of oxygen on Pt₃Ni(111).

In the next step, n-EC-STM measurements were performed to determine the active sites responsible for the superior ORR performance compared to pure Pt(111). Figure S3 in the SI illustrates the working principle of this technique, as introduced

in previous works.^{11,12} In n-EC-STM, the electrolyte serves as tunnelling medium. The sample potential can be varied such that a reaction at the electrode-electrolyte interface is enabled (reaction “on”) or hindered (reaction “off”). When the reaction is turned “on”, the noise level is increased compared to reaction “off”, when the tip is scanning across an active site. The reason is that the stability of the STM signal depends on the tunnelling barrier, which is governed by changes in the electrolyte,⁵⁸ molecules being adsorbed on the electrode surface⁵⁹ and the movement of species within the tunnelling gap.⁶⁰ Note that “STM signal” can either refer to tip-sample distance (height) or tunnelling current, dependent on the chosen mode. The distinct and confined noise level increase of the STM signal over the active sites can be exploited to *in-situ* locate them. To determine the sample potentials that can be assigned to reaction “on” and “off”, a CV is recorded in the EC-STM setup against the Pt *quasi*-reference electrode (Figure S3c). A potential of 0 mV_{Pt} is chosen as reaction “off” as the respective sample current is zero. For reaction “on”, a negative potential was applied to the sample. Experimental parameters such as the potential for reaction “on”, current set-point and tip potential are given in Table S1 of the SI.

Figure 2 depicts an n-EC-STM measurement across the flat (111) surface containing a single step (marked with a white line). During the scan, the sample potential was alternated between 0 mV_{Pt} (“off”) and -100 mV_{Pt} (ORR “on”). When the reaction is turned “on”, a considerable increase in the noise level is

observed compared to when no reaction takes place. This noise manifests as irregularly occurring values of high intensity in the STM signal, which can be seen as white dots in the STM image and spikes in the corresponding profile (line scans as given in Figure 2b). On the (111) terrace, the noise is homogeneously distributed leading to the conclusion that the surface is consisting of equally active sites. Additional confirmation that terrace sites are homogeneously active and show a comparable noise level, and thus similar activity, is included in Figure S4 of the SI, where an n-EC-STM measurement was performed across a flat surface. In the region of the step edge, the noise seems to have the same extent as for terrace sites. In Figure 2b, line scans (height profile in scan direction) across the step are given for both reaction “on” and “off”. The position of the step is marked by a diamond-shaped red pin. It seems that the noise level (height and density of the spikes) is similar at step and terrace sites.

The qualitative indications provided by the STM images can be strengthened by a quantitative approach.¹² First, the data was divided into step and terrace sites. The data points assigned to step sites were extracted from the centre of the step to a scan size of 5 nm in each direction. In the corresponding waterfall plot (Figure 2b), the position of the step is marked by the red diamond-shaped pin and the arrow around the pin indicate the data attributed to the step sites. Another arrow marks the dataset for terrace sites, which was also confined to a width of 10 nm. Second, the STM signal (height *z*) was derived with respect to adjacent data points (in scan/*x*-direction) recorded

Figure 1. Surface science and electrochemical investigation of the freshly prepared Pt₃Ni(111) surface. a) LEED image. b) High-resolution LT-STM image confirming the (111) orientation. (tip-sample bias: -10.0 mV; tip set-point: 3.0 nA) c) CV in Ar-saturated 0.1 M HClO₄ at a scan rate of 50 mV s⁻¹. d) Anodic scan of polarization curve in O₂-saturated 0.1 M HClO₄, recorded at 1600 rpm and a scan rate of 50 mV s⁻¹, 85% iR-corrected.

during the scan ($\delta z/\delta x$). Third, histograms of these signal derivatives were rendered using a bin size of 0.2 for all images. To account for different sizes of datasets, the histograms are normalized to the amount of data points taken for the respective dataset (“normalized counts”). Following a quantification approach reported previously,¹² the histograms were fitted by a Gaussian distribution and the full width at half maximum (FWHM) was extracted to quantify the noise level. The correlation between the FWHM and the noise level is the following: at a low noise level, there is not much distortion to the signal and the corresponding histogram shows a narrow distribution with a small FWHM. Analogously, at a high noise level, the signal experiences distinct fluctuations and shows a broad histogram with a large FWHM. Figure 2c and d give the histograms for step and terrace sites, respectively, and compare reaction “off” (black) and “on” (turquoise). If no reaction takes place, the histogram is narrow and thus indicates a low noise level. Conversely, when the ORR is ongoing, the histogram broadens, hinting toward a high noise level. The FWHM and height of the Gaussian fit, which serve as a measure for the noise level, are listed in Table S2 of the SI for all n-EC-STM measurements. Interestingly, there is no significant difference in the noise level of step and terrace under reaction conditions, suggesting that these sites are equally active.

Aiming for statistical soundness, more n-EC-STM images were recorded. In Figure 3, where two regular step edges of the (111) surface are visible. In the first part of the image, the reaction was switched “off”, while the second part, recorded at $-50\text{ mV}_{\text{Pt}}$, marks the onset of the reaction (see CV in Figure S3c). In the following, the potential was lowered stepwise to $-200\text{ mV}_{\text{Pt}}$, which is equivalent to an increase in ORR current. In the last part, the reaction was switched off to confirm the “reversibility” of the noise. We observe that the overall extent of the noise level is stronger with increasing “overpotential”. In Figure 3a, the noise level increase, which is linked to the activity, is comparable for step and terrace sites. This can be seen more easily in the corresponding line scans in Figure 3b, taken for the step on the left side. Line scans across the left step edge exclude the potential of $-150\text{ mV}_{\text{Pt}}$, as it drifted out of the scan range at a potential of $-200\text{ mV}_{\text{Pt}}$. Additional, quantitative confirmation is given in the histograms in Figure 3c,d. For each applied potential, the FWHMs of step and terrace sites are comparable. Besides, it becomes apparent that the overall noise level increases with decreasing potential. This is understandable since an increased reaction rate leads to stronger fluctuations in the tunnelling medium and, thus, noise in the signal.¹² Additional measurements are included in Figure S5 and Figure S6 of the SI. While in Figure S5 step and terrace sites are comparably active, in the case of Figure S6 the step sites are less active than terrace sites.

Figure 2. a) n-EC-STM measurement of a flat $\text{Pt}_3\text{Ni}(111)$ surface containing a single step edge marked by a white line. When the reaction is turned “on”, a considerable increase in the noise level is detected. From the extent of the noise level, we conclude that terrace sites show similar activity compared to step sites. b) Line scans across the step edge in a. The centre of the step is marked by a red diamond-shaped pin. c,d) Histograms of step and terrace sites. From the FWHM of the Gaussian fit, it can be assumed that terrace and step sites contribute comparably to the overall activity. Color code: “off” (black), “on” (green).

In summary, from the n-EC-STM measurements, we can conclude that the Pt₃Ni(111) surface consists solely of active sites, which is deduced from the homogeneous appearance of the recorded noise. The occurrence of active Pt₃Ni(111) terrace sites becomes understandable when comparing the binding energy of *OH on Pt₃Ni(111) to Pt(111). Calculations show that an optimal ORR catalyst should bind *OH approx. 0.10 eV to 0.15 eV weaker than Pt(111).¹ From experimental data,¹³ it was extracted that Pt₃Ni(111) binds *OH approx. 0.13 eV weaker than Pt(111).⁶¹ This shows that the binding of intermediates is almost optimal on Pt₃Ni(111) surfaces, explaining why the most active sites cannot be located on more coordinated sites.⁶² Further experimental reports confirm the high activity of the Pt₃Ni(111) surface. For low-index Pt₃Ni(hkl) surfaces, the order of activity was reported as Pt₃Ni(100) < Pt₃Ni(110) ≪ Pt₃Ni(111).¹³ In a study on nanoparticles, Pt₃Ni particles of octahedral shape exposing (111) facets showed superior activity to cubic shapes exposing (100) facets.⁶³ It is important to note that these nanoparticles typically need to be stabilized by introducing foreign atoms such as Ga, Mo or Rh.^{64,65,66,67} The role of step sites in the catalytic process is difficult to evaluate. Hoshi *et al.* studied stepped Pt₃Ni(111) single crystals to probe the role of (111) and (110) step sites on the ORR activity.⁵³ They concluded that an increasing number of (111) steps decreases the activity. In contrast, Pt[n(111)x(100)] crystals outperform

Pt(111) and show an optimal performance between n = 3 and n = 5. Evidently, sites at or close to (100) steps are more active than (111) steps or regular (111) terraces. In our study, we observed step sites of inferior (Figure S5) and equal (Figure 2, Figure 3, Figure S4) activity compared to terrace sites. Unfortunately, n-EC-STM is not able to access the orientation of the step edges. With these reports in mind, one can assume that the highly active step edges are presumably oriented in a (100) fashion whereas the less active steps may be (111). However, for a more profound statement of the nature of active sites on Pt₃Ni(111), we substantiate our experimental findings with mathematical modelling.

4. Elucidating Active Sites using Alloy-Sensitive Generalized Coordination Numbers

The simplest geometric descriptor for active sites at pure metal surfaces is the coordination number (CN), which is a count of the nearest neighbours around the active site, assuming that all neighbours are identical and equivalent to those in the bulk. A first-order extension called “generalized coordination number” (GCN) allows distinguishing between inequivalent nearest neighbours by considering the second-nearest neighbours in the count.^{20,68} In doing so, it is feasible to capture finite-size effects and directly compare sites at nanoparticles and

Figure 3. a) n-EC-STM measurement of two regular step edges on the Pt₃Ni(111) surface. During the recording of the image, the potential was varied according to the colour code. With decreasing potential (*i.e.* increasing ORR current), the noise features get more pronounced and a higher density of high-intensity spots is observed. The noise level of step and terrace sites seems comparable. b) Waterfall plot comprising the high profile in scan direction across the step marked in a). From the data, histograms for the c) step and d) terrace sites were compiled. The histograms broaden and lose intensity with increasingly negative potential, suggesting a higher noise level. For each potential, the curves for step and terrace sites are comparable, leading to the assumption of their similar ORR activity.

extended surfaces and make activity predictions.^{69,70} Moreover, compression or stretching can be incorporated in simple terms in the generalized coordination numbers (denoted \overline{CN}^*).⁵⁰ However, neither the conventional nor the GCNs are suitable for alloys, where ligand effects are present, often in combination with strain effects. So far, this has prevented the making of a unified geometric picture for alloys and pure metals, and motivated the elaboration of more sophisticated descriptors.⁷¹

A step forward is taken in Figure 4a, which provides a simple method for incorporating alloying effects into the \overline{CN}^* . First, a calibration curve with small mean and maximum absolute errors (MAE = 0.03 eV, MAX = 0.10 eV) is made based on *OH binding energies and the \overline{CN}^* . Subsequently, the curve is used to estimate the \overline{CN}^* of sites at Pt₃Ni and Pt₃Co alloys, as shown in the top inset of Figure 4a. From the difference between those numbers and the values obtained for analogous pure Pt sites, it is possible to calculate the equivalence of a Ni or Co neighbour in terms of Pt neighbours (denoted n_M in Figure 4a). On average, we find that Ni and Co atoms are equivalent to 1.59 and 1.48 Pt atoms, respectively (Figure 4a, bottom inset). These values can

be used to assess the \overline{CN}^* on all sorts of geometric sites on Pt₃M alloys.

To illustrate the predictive power of the alloy-sensitive \overline{CN}^* , consider Pt₃Ni(111) terraces as an example. Their *OH binding energies are 1.10 eV which, according to the regression in Figure 4a, corresponds to $\overline{CN}^* = 8.05$. This differs from the value of pristine Pt(111) terraces ($\overline{CN}^* = 7.5$) by 0.55 coordination units, such that a Ni neighbour in the second layer is equivalent to 1.55 Pt neighbours. In the SI, **section S5.3**, the procedure is shown in detail and the values are tabulated for all Pt₃Ni and Pt₃Co sites under study.

For PtCu NSAs the procedure is analogous, except that the subsurface Cu coverage and the number of Cu neighbours around the active sites need to be considered. Once the \overline{CN}^* of the alloy sites are known, their ORR activities can be predicted with the coordination-activity plot in Figure 4b, which correlates the ORR limiting potential (ΔU) and the generalized coordination of the active sites.²⁰

Several observations can be made and are listed in the following. As a side note, these findings support the

Figure 4. Computational modelling of the ORR on Pt-based electrocatalysts. a) DFT-calculated binding energies of *OH on a wide variety of pure Pt sites. The linear fit together with its associated mean and maximum absolute errors (MAE, MAX) are provided. The grey band around the linear fit corresponds to ± 2 MAE. Top inset: assessment of the generalized coordination numbers of surface sites at Pt₃Ni and Pt₃Co using the correlation found in the main panel. The orange lines indicate the procedure. Bottom inset: assessment of the equivalence of Ni and Co neighbours in terms of Pt neighbours based on the generalized coordination numbers obtained in the top inset. b) Coordination-activity plot for sites at pure Pt (white), Pt₃Ni (blue), Pt₃Co (red) and PtCu near-surface alloys (green; the subsurface coverage of Cu in ML is provided in each case). The most common potential-determining steps are shown on each side of the plot. The grey band around the black lines corresponds to ± 2 MAE. T: terrace site, B: step-bottom site, s: strained site. c) Activity enhancement with respect to Pt(111) as a function of the average generalized coordination number of the electrocatalysts, see **section S5.5**.

experimental results introduced and discussed in **section 3**, and the activity measurements on bulk single crystals of the past^{24,53, 72}. However, they provide insights, which go beyond these reports:

- Pt₃Ni(111) terraces (Pt₃Ni(111)-T) are the most active sites, while some terrace sites near step edges are close in activity (e.g. Pt₃Ni(221)-T), and step-bottom sites are less active (e.g. Pt₃Ni(221)-B).
- Although Pt₃Co(111) terraces (Pt₃Co(111)-T) are considerably more active than Pt(111), they are less active than Pt₃Ni(111) terraces.
- Pt sites strained as much as in Pt₃Ni ($s = 2.31\%$) but with no Ni neighbours are more active than Pt(111); depending on the geometry of the active site, they can be more or less active than sites with Ni neighbours. In particular, the limiting potential of step-bottom sites at strained Pt(533) (s-Pt(533)-B) is similar to that of Pt₃Ni(111) terraces (Pt₃Ni(111)-T), suggesting that step bottom areas with low or no Ni content can be rather active for the ORR.
- Near-surface alloys of Pt and submonolayer amounts of Cu are more active than Pt(111), and 0.5 ML Cu in the subsurface render Pt(111) sites nearly as active as Pt₃Ni(111) terraces because of ligand effects.
- Step-edge sites are rather undercoordinated ($\overline{CN}^* \approx 6.0$), bind *OH strongly, and hence display a low ORR activity, see **section S5.3** in the SI.

It is viable to go further than the coordination-activity plot to predict the overall activity of the catalysts by virtue of the individual contributions of their active sites. This is done in Figure 4c, where we correlate the average \overline{CN}^* of several Pt-based electrocatalysts and their enhancement with respect to Pt(111) (calculated using the Butler-Volmer equation, see **section S5.4** in the SI). Figure 4c confirms that Pt₃Ni(111) is close to the top of the volcano plot and that step edges (as found in Pt₃Ni(221) and Pt₃Ni(533)) lower the activity. Nonetheless, the enhancement of all Pt₃Ni alloys compared to Pt(111) is substantial. Pt₃Co(111) is less active than Pt₃Ni(111) and (100) steps defects render slightly less active alloy surfaces. Last but not least, PtCu(111) NSAs are also highly active and a subsurface coverage of 0.5 ML Cu is close in activity to Pt₃Ni(111). Details on the assessment of $\ln[j / j_{\text{Pt}(111)}]$ can be found in the SI, **section S5.4**. In sum, Figure 4 provides a means for creating alloy-sensitive electrocatalysis models with generalized coordination numbers. This opens the path toward the computational design of electrocatalytic active sites with structural and compositional predictive power.

Conclusions

We applied n-EC-STM on a Pt₃Ni(111) single crystal to identify the active sites towards the ORR in acidic medium. We found that the most active sites are located on the basal plane Pt₃Ni(111). Here, a homogeneously increased noise level suggests that all sites are equally active. Step sites were found to be either slightly less or similarly active compared to terraces. Furthermore, we devised alloy-sensitive generalized

coordination numbers and created site-specific and material-specific ORR activity plots. Co, Ni and Cu increase the generalized coordination of Pt surface sites by virtue of strain and/or ligand effects. We observed that the interplay of such effects is nearly optimal in Pt₃Ni(111) but insufficient to reach the top of the activity plot for Pt₃Co(111). Ligand effects in PtCu also enhance the activity with respect to pure Pt depending on the subsurface Cu coverage. With this comprehensive report, we expand the knowledge of active sites for the ORR from pure Pt to Pt alloys in acidic medium.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Acknowledgements

The authors cordially thank Mr. Karl Eberle for his valuable assistance in the sample preparation and Mr. Kun-Ting Song for his help with some of the electrochemical experiments.

RMK, RWH, BG and ASB acknowledge financial support from the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG), in the framework of the projects BA 5795/3-1 and BA 5795/4-1, and under Germany's Excellence Strategy-EXC 2089/1-390776260, cluster of excellence 'e-conversion'. AR acknowledges funding by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) – 453903355. FCV acknowledges financial support from Spanish MICIUN through RTI2018-095460-B-I00 and María de Maeztu (MDM-2017-0767) grants and a Ramón y Cajal research contract (RYC-2015-18996), and also from Generalitat de Catalunya (grant 2017SGR13). The use of supercomputing facilities at SURFsara was sponsored by NWO Physical Sciences, with financial support from NWO. TOS and ASB acknowledge funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement HERMES No. 952184.

References

- 1 A.S. Arico, P. Bruce, B. Scrosati, J.M. Tarascon, W. van Schalkwijk, *Nature Mater.*, 2005, **4**, 366-377.
- 2 W.T. Yu, M.D. Porosoff, J.G.G. Chen, *Chem. Rev.*, 2012, **112**, 5780-5817.
- 3 K. Sasaki, H. Naohara, Y. Choi, Y. Cai, W. Chen, P. Liu, R.R. Adzic, *Nature Commun.*, 2012, **3**, 1-5.
- 4 J. K. Nørskov, J. Rossmeisl, A. Logadottir, L. Lindqvist, J. R. Kitchin, T. Bligaard, H.J. Jónsson, *Phys. Chem. B*, 2004, **108**, 17886-17892.
- 5 N. M. Marković, P.N. Ross, *Surf. Sci. Rep.*, 2002, **45**, 117-229.
- 6 A. S. Bandarenka, M.T.M. Koper, *J. Catal.*, 2013, **308**, 11-24.
- 7 R. Rizo, E. Herrero, J.M. Feliu, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2013, **15**, 15416-15425.
- 8 A. Hitotsuyanagi, M. Nakamura, N. Hoshi, *Electrochim. Acta*, 2012, **82**, 512-516.
- 9 A. Kuzume, E. Herrero, J. M. Feliu, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 2007, **599**, 333-343.
- 10 F. Calle-Vallejo, M. D. Pohl, D. Reinisch, D. Loffreda, P. Sautet, A. S. Bandarenka, *Chem. Sci.*, 2017, **8**, 2283-2289.
- 11 J. H. Pfisterer, Y. Liang, O. Schneider, A. S. Bandarenka, *Nature*, 2017, **549**, 74-77.
- 12 R. W. Haid, R. M. Kluge, Y. Liang, A. S. Bandarenka, *Small Methods*, 2020, **4**, 2000710.
- 13 V. R. Stamenković, B. Fowler, B. S. Mun, G. Wang, P. N. Ross, C. A. Lucas, N. M. Marković, *Science*, 2007, **315**, 493-497.
- 14 C. Chen, Y. Kang, Z. Huo, Z. Zhu, W. Huang, H. L. Xin, J. D. Snyder, D. Li, J. A. Herron, M. Mavrikakis, M. Chi, K. L. More, Y. Li, N. M. Marković, G. A. Somorjai, P. Yang, V. R. Stamenković, *Science*, 2014, **343**, 1339-1343.
- 15 J. Kibsgaard, Y. Gorlin, Z. Chen, T. F. Jaramillo, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2012, **134**, 7758-7765.
- 16 R. Chattot, T. Asset, P. Bordet, J. Drnec, L. Dubau, F. Maillard, *ACS Catal.*, 2017, **7**, 398-408.
- 17 J. Fichtner, S. Watzel, B. Garlyyev, R.M. Kluge, F. Haimerl, H.A. El-Sayed, W. Li, F.M. Maillard, L. Dubau, R. Chattot, J. Michalička, J. M. Macak, W. Wang, D. Wang, T. Gigl, C. Hugenschmidt, A. S. Bandarenka, *ACS Catal.*, 2020, **10**, 3131-3142.
- 18 J. Greeley, I.E.L Stephens, A.S. Bondarenko, T.P. Johansson, H.A. Hansen, T.F. Jaramillo, J. Rossmeisl, I. Chorkendorff, J.K. Nørskov, *Nat. Chem.*, 2009, **1**, 552-556.
- 19 V.R. Stamenković, B.S. Mun, K.J.J. Mayrhofer, P.N. Ross, N.M. Marković, J. Rossmeisl, J. Greeley, J.K. Nørskov, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2006, **45**, 2897-2901.
- 20 F. Calle-Vallejo, J. Tymoczko, V. Colic, Q. Huy Vu, M. D. Pohl, K. Morgenstern, D. Loffreda, P. Sautet, W. Schuhmann, A. S. Bandarenka, *Science*, 2015, **350**, 185-189.
- 21 M. Escudero-Escribano, P. Malacrida, M. H. Hansen, U. G. Vej-Hansen, A. Velázquez-Palenzuela, V. Tripkovic, J. Schiøtz, J. Rossmeisl, I. E. L. Stephens, I. Chorkendorff, *Science*, 2016, **352**, 73-76.
- 22 M. Liu, Z. Zhao, X. Duan, Y. Huang, *Adv. Mater.* 2019, **31**, 1802234.
- 23 J. Fichtner, B. Garlyyev, S. Watzel, H.A. El-Sayed, J.N. Schwämmlein, W. Li, F.M. Maillard, L. Dubau, J. Michalička, J.M. Macak, A. Holleitner, A.S. Bandarenka, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, 2019, **11**, 5129-5135.
- 24 I. E. L. Stephens, A. S. Bondarenko, F. J. Perez-Alonso, F. Calle-Vallejo, L. Bech, T. P. Johansson, A. K. Jepsen, R. Frydendal, B. P. Knudsen, J. Rossmeisl, I. Chorkendorff, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2011, **133**, 5485-5491.
- 25 F. Calle-Vallejo, M. T. M. Koper, A. S. Bandarenka, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2013, **42**, 5210-5230.
- 26 L. Gan, C. Cui, M. Heggen, F. Dionigi, S. Rudi, P. Strasser, *Science*, 2014, **346**, 1502-1506.
- 27 M. Escudero-Escribano, A. Verdaguier-Casadevall, P. Malacrida, U. Grønberg, B. P. Knudsen, A. K. Jepsen, J. Rossmeisl, I. E. Stephens, I. Chorkendorff, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2012, **134**, 16476-16479.
- 28 S. Mi, N. Cheng, H. Jiang, C. Li, H. Jiang, *RSC Adv.* 2018, **8**, 15344-15351.
- 29 X. Tian, X. Zhao, Y. Su, L. Wang, H. Wang, D. Dang, B. Chi, H. Liu, E.J.M. Hensen, X.W. Lou, B.Y. Xia, *Science*, 2019, **366**, 850-856.
- 30 Y.-J. Wang, N. Zhao, B. Fang, H. Li, X.T. Bi, H. Wang, H., *Chem. Rev.*, 2015, **115**, 3433-3467.
- 31 F. Maroun, F. Ozanam, O. M. Magnussen, R. J. Behm, *Science*, 2001, **293**, 1811-1814.
- 32 J. R. Kitchin, J. K. Nørskov, M. A. Barteau, J. G. Chen, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 2015, **120**, 10240-10246.
- 33 Q. Jia, W. Liang, M.K. Bates, P. Mani, W. Lee, S. Mukerjee, *ACS Nano*, 2015, **9**, 387-400.
- 34 I. E. L Stephens, A.S. Bondarenko, U. Gronberg, J. Rossmeisl, I. Chorkendorff, *Energy Environ. Sci.*, 2012, **5**, 6744-6762.
- 35 C. Wang, M. Chi, D. Li, D. Strmcnik, D. van der Vliet, G. Wang, V. Komanicky, K.-C. Chang, A.P. Paulikas, D. Tripkovic, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2011, **133**, 14396-14403.
- 36 Y. Liang, D. McLaughlin, C. Csoklich, O. Schneider, A. S.

- Bandarenka, *Energy Environ. Sci.*, 2019, **12**, 351-357.
- 37 Y. Liang, C. Csoklich, D. McLaughlin, O. Schneider, A. S. Bandarenka, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, 2019, **11**, 12476-12480.
- 38 E. Mitterreiter, Y. Liang, M. Golibrzuch, D. McLaughlin, C. Csoklich, J. D. Bartl, A. Holleitner, U. Wurstbauer, A. S. Bandarenka, *npj 2D Mater. Appl.*, 2019, **3**, 1.
- 39 R. M. Kluge, R. W. Haid, A. S. Bandarenka, *J. Catal.*, 2021, **396**, 14-22.
- 40 R. M. Kluge, R. W. Haid, I. E. L. Stephens, F. Calle-Vallejo, A. S. Bandarenka, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2021, **23**, 10051-10058.
- 41 R. W. Haid, R. M. Kluge, T. O. Schmidt, A. S. Bandarenka, *Electrochim. Acta*, 2021, **382**, 138285.
- 42 T. Kosmala, A. Baby, M. Lunardon, D. Perilli, H. Liu, C. Durante, C. Di Valentin, S. Agnoli, G. Granozzi, *Nat. Catal.*, 2021, **4**, 850-859.
- 43 I. Horcas, R. Fernández, J. M. Gómez-Rodríguez, J. Colchero, J. Gómez-Herrero, A. M. Baro, *Rev Sci Instrum.*, 2007, **78**, 013705.
- 44 T. J. Schmidt, H. A. Gasteiger, G. D. Stab, P. M. Urban, D. M. Kolb, R. J. Behm, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1998, **145**, 2354-2358.
- 45 L. A. Nagahara, T. Thundat, S. M. Lindsay, *Rev. Sci. Instrum.*, 1989, **60**, 3128-3130.
- 46 G. Kresse, J. Furthmüller, *Phys. Rev. B*, 1996, **54**, 11169-11186.
- 47 J. P. Perdew, K. Burke, M. Ernzerhof, *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 1996, **77**, 3865-3868
- 48 G. Kresse, D. Joubert, *Phys. Rev. B*, 1999, **59**, 1758-1775.
- 49 H. J. Monkhorst, J. D. Pack, *Phys. Rev. B*, 1976, **13**, 5188-5192.
- 50 F. Calle-Vallejo, A. S. Bandarenka, *ChemSusChem* 2018, **11**, 1824-1828.
- 51 A. W. E. Chan, R. Hoffmann, W. Ho, *Langmuir* 1992, **8**, 1111-1119.
- 52 J. Kim, W. H. Doh, H. Kondoh, K. Mase, J.-J. Gallet, F. Bournel, B. S. Mun, J. Y. Park, *J. Electron Spectrosc. Relat. Phenom.*, 2020, **238**, 146857.
- 53 T. Rurigaki, A. Hitotsuyanagi, M. Nakamura, N. Sakai, N. Hoshi, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 2014, **716**, 58-62.
- 54 P. Strasser, S. Koh, T. Anniyev, J. Greeley, K. Moore, C. Yu, Z. Liu, S. Kaya, D. Nordlund, H. Ogasawara, M.F. Toney, A. Nilsson, *Nat. Chem.*, 2010, **2**, 454-460.
- 55 Z. Duan, G. Wang, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2011, **13**, 20178-20187.
- 56 S. Kattel, G. Wang, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 2014, **141**, 124713.
- 57 T.-Y. Jeon, S.J. Yoo, Y.-H. Cho, K.-S. Lee, S.H. Kang, Y.-E. Sung, *J. Phys. Chem. C*, 2009, **113**, 19732-19739.
- 58 M. Hugelmann, W. Schindler, *Surface Sci.*, 2003, **541**, L643-L648.
- 59 M. Sumetskii, A. A. Kornyshev, U. Stimming, *Surf. Sci.*, 1994, **307**, 23-27.
- 60 M. Sumetskii, A. A. Kornyshev, *Phys. Rev. B*, 1993, **48**, 17493-17506.
- 61 V. Čolić, A.S. Bandarenka, *ACS Catal.*, 2016, **6**, 5378-5385.
- 62 V. Čolić, A.S. Bandarenka, *ACS Catal.*, 2016, **6**, 5378-5385.
- 63 J. Zhang, H. Z. Yang, J. Y. Fang, S. Z. Zou, *Nano Lett.*, 2010, **10**, 638-644.
- 64 X. Huang, Z. Zhao, L. Cao, Y. Chen, E. Zhu, Z. Lin, M. Li, A. Yan, A. Zettl, Y. M. Wang, X. Duan, T. Mueller, Y. Huang, *Science*, 2015, **348**, 1230-1234.
- 65 Q. Jia, Z. Zhao, L. Cao, J. Li, S. Ghoshal, V. Davies, E. Stavitski, K. Attenkofer, Z. Liu, M. Li, X. Duan, S. Mukerjee, T. Mueller, Y. Huang, *Nano Lett.*, 2018, **18**, 798-804.
- 66 J. Lim, H. Shin, M. Kim, H. Lee, K.-S. Lee, Y. Kwon, D. Song, S. Oh, H. Kim, E. Cho, *Nano Lett.*, 2018, **18**, 2450-2458.
- 67 V. Beermann, M. Gocyla, E. Willinger, S. Rudi, M. Heggen, R. E. Dunin-Borkowski, M.-G. Willinger, P. Strasser, *Nano Lett.*, 2016, **16**, 1719-1725.
- 68 F. Calle-Vallejo, J. I. Martínez, J. M. García-Lastra, P. Sautet, D. Loffreda, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2014, **53**, 8316-8319.
- 69 K. Rossi, G. G. Asara, F. Baletto, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2019, **21**, 4888-4898.
- 70 M. Rück, A. S. Bandarenka, F. Calle-Vallejo, A. Gagliardi, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.*, 2018, **9**, 4463-4468.
- 71 X. Ma, H. Xin, *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 2017, **118**, 036101.
- 72 Y. Takesue, M. Nakamura, N. Hoshi, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2014, **16**, 13774-13779.